

is suggested on the basis that these are soluble in non-polar solvent benzene. That these adducts are genuine complexes and not stoichiometric mixtures is also clear from the fact that these complexes decompose at a temperature much higher than the boiling point of ethylenediamine. The complexes in absence of excess of ethylenediamine decompose in non-aqueous solvents, leaving the insoluble metal salts. As such conductivity values could not be ascertained.

An examination of the infrared spectra of alkali-metal-ethylenediamine complexes shows (Table 2)

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1})

Li8HQ.en	3390	3200 1610	1330 1020 810	795
KSaIH.en	3370	3200 1605sh	1320 1030 820sh	810
LiSaIA.en	3370	3180 1605	1295 1020 825	820
NaSaIA.en	3360	3200 1600sh	1320 1025 810	800sh
LiAnth.en	3380	3270 1610	1320 1028 822	800
NaAnth.en	3450 3400 3340		1040 825	820sh

sh=shoulder.

that different NH_2 vibrations are present in the complexes; though in some cases the vibrations of the acid-salts of alkali metals overlap the NH_2 vibrations. When these frequencies are compared with those obtained for Zn, Cd and Hg³, there seems no doubt, that *en* group in all these compounds has the same configuration.

The two N-H stretching vibrations appear as medium peaks between $3400\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The 3377 cm^{-1} peak of ethylenediamine remains unaffected after complexation, but the 3316 cm^{-1} peak is very much affected in the complexes. This appears at 3200 cm^{-1} with reduced intensity in the complexes thereby suggesting that there has been decrease in the bond order of N-H on complexation. The NH_2 bend vibration can be located as a single sharp peak (or shoulder) at 1605 cm^{-1} region. The ligand vibrations of the acid-salts very much interfere with the NH_2 bend vibrations. The NH_2 wag and twist appear at 1320 and 1020 cm^{-1} region as weak or medium peak.

On comparing the vibrations of NH_2 in ethylenediamine in alkali-metal salt-ethylenediamine complexes with that of 'standards'⁴ whose structures are already known, it is suggested that, because of the similarity and simpleness of the spectra, ethylenediamine has a bridging *trans*-structure.

Further to have more evidence regarding the *trans*-structure, the CH_2 rocking region $870\text{--}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$, were also looked into. In all the complexes two peaks appeared between $820\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which further points to *trans*-structure⁵.

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Studies on Vanadium (V)-N-*m*-Tolyl-*p*-Methoxy-Benzohydroxamic Acid Complex

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N-*m*-TOLYL-*p*-METHOXYBENZOHYDROXAMIC acid (TMBHA) has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) by solvent extraction technique¹. The present paper deals with the determination of dissociation constant of the reagent (TMBHA) from the extraction data analysis and evaluation of the stepwise stability constants of its complex with vanadium(V). The Yatsimirskii's^{2,3} and Leden's⁴ graphical extrapolation methods were applied with necessary modification⁵ to calculate the values of stepwise stability constants. The overall stability constants of the complex also have been determined by Job's⁶ and Harvey and Manning's⁷ methods.

Experimental

Reagent and solutions: A stock solution of V(V) was prepared by dissolving vanadium pentoxide (A.R.; B.D.H.) in dilute hydrochloric acid and the vanadium content was determined by standard methods⁸.

N-m-Tolyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) was synthesised by known methods⁹. A fresh solution of the reagent was prepared in pure chloroform.

Apparatus: An ELICO pH meter with glass and saturated calomel electrode was employed for pH adjustments. Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with quartz cells of 1.00 cm light path was used for all photometric measurements. All measurements were made at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

General Procedure: An aliquot of the vanadium(V) solution was taken and to it added enough concentrated hydrochloric acid so as to make acid strength about 4.0 M. Total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with double distilled

water and equilibrated with 10 ml of the reagent solution in chloroform. After equilibration, two phases were separated and the absorbance of the extracted violet coloured vanadium complex was noted at 530 nm against similarly processed reagent solution as a blank. The vanadium extracted was computed from the appropriate calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra of TMBHA : The absorption spectrum of the TMBHA solution in chloroform against the pure chloroform blank shows maximum absorbance at 255 nm. The molar absorptivity of the reagent at 255 nm is 1.50×10^4 . The reagent follows Beer's law in the concentration range of $0.33 - 15.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ in chloroform at 255 nm.

Distribution of reagent : A 10 ml solution of the reagent, HR, of known concentration, $[HR]_{tot}$ in chloroform was equilibrated with equal volume of aqueous solution at pH 1.0-12.0 and ionic strength of 0.2 M as maintained by $NaClO_4$. The concentration of the reagent in organic phase, $[HR]_{org}$ was determined by noting the absorbance of the solution at 255 nm against the similarly processed chloroform as a blank and reading from the calibration curve. The distribution of reagent, (D_R) is then :

$$D_R = [HR]_{org} / ([HR]_{tot} - [HR]_{org})$$

The results obtained from the distribution study of TMBHA in chloroform-water system are incorporated in Fig. 1. The distribution decreases above pH 10.0 which may be attributed to the dissociation of the proton from =NOH group of TMBHA.

Fig. 1. Distribution of reagent as a function of pH.

Proton-ligand stability constants : If K_1^H is the proton-ligand association constant, P_R the partition constant of reagent HR, then the distribution ratio may be given as^{1,0}

$$\frac{1}{D_R} = \frac{1}{P_R} \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_1^H [H^+]} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

At low pH, $D_R = P_R$. Thus, Fig. 1 gives the value of $\log P_R$. The $\log P_R$ for TMBHA between chloroform and water is found to be 1.54. The negative slope region of Fig. 1 holds the relation

$$\log \left(\frac{P_R - D_R}{D_R} \right) = pH - \log K_1^H$$

This gives the value of $\log K_1^H$ (10.85) for TMBHA (Fig. 2). The value of $\log K_1^H$ was also found and compared by potentiometric¹¹ (10.91) and spectrophotometric⁸ (11.20) methods. The values as found by various methods agree well with each other.

Fig. 2. $\log \frac{P_R - D_R}{D_R}$ as function of pH.

Composition and formation constants of the complex :

The composition studies of the extractable V(V)-TMBHA complex have been made by earlier workers¹. The studies reveal that vanadium forms 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex with TMBHA in strong hydrochloric acid medium.

Stepwise formation constants for 1 : 2 system was calculated following Yatsimirskii's^{2,3} and

Leden's⁴ methods. The equilibrium ligand concentrations and the degree of complex formation were calculated from Beer's law data. The various functions were constructed and evaluated in the manner stated earlier⁵.

The overall stability constant of the complex was determined by Job's⁶ method and Harvey and Manning's⁷ method. The values of stability constants as evaluated by various methods are compiled in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR V(V)-TMBHA COMPLEX AT 30±1°C

Method	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
Yatsimirskii's	5.11	4.68	9.79
Leden's	4.93	4.64	9.57
Job's	—	—	9.50
Harvey-Manning's	—	—	9.42

It seems from Table 1 that, the overall conditional metal-ligand stability constants as well as stepwise stability constants obtained by various methods agree well with each other.

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Spectrophotometric Studies of Lanthanide Complexes with 1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-Naphthol(PAN) in Water-Ethanol Medium

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SEVERAL reports have appeared in the literature on the studies of the formation of rare earth metal complexes with 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol(PAN) and their extraction from aqueous solution into various organic solvents¹⁻¹⁰. However, conflicting reports appeared in the literature regarding the composition of the extracted species, for example, Shibata⁸ reported a composition of 1 : 2 Navrátil⁴ 1 : 4 while Chang Tiao-Hsu and co-workers⁹ reported a composition of 1 : 3. We described in our earlier communications^{11,12} detailed solvent extraction characteristics and the preparation of lanthanide-PAN complexes in solid state and proposed an octahedral structure with a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 3. In continuation of our earlier studies, we are now incorporating in this communication the results of our spectrophotometric study of these complexes in water-ethanol medium.

Experimental

Photometric measurements were carried out on Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer and Spekol spectrocoulometer using 1 cm corex cells. A Toshniwal Digital (Model CL 46) pH meter with a combined calomel-glass electrode was used for pH measurements.

Stock solutions of lanthanide metals were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of pure oxides (Apachae Chemicals, USA or E. Merck, Germany) in perchloric acid. The solutions were standardised with a standard solution of EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator¹³.

1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol(Riedel) was recrystallised from ethanol. A stock solution was prepared by dissolving 0.2493 gm of the dye in 100 ml of ethanol. Its strength was checked up by a photometric titration¹⁴.

Ammonium hydroxide and ammonium chloride buffers were prepared in the pH range 8-10. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. All experiments were carried out at room temperature (28±1°) and the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1±0.01 with NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer.

Recommended procedure for the photometric determination :

To an aliquot of the test solution containing (1-6 ml of 3×10⁻⁵ M) rare earth metal ion in a